

Application of Sentiment Analysis in Libraries: Prospect of Enhancing Book Recommendations and Collection Development through User Feedback Analysis

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Abstract: *The integration of sentiment analysis into library services presents a promising opportunity to enhance book recommendation systems and improve collection development through user feedback analysis. This paper explores the application of sentiment analysis used to assess the emotional tone in user-generated content—in the context of libraries. By analyzing user reviews, social media discussions, and other forms of feedback, libraries can gain deeper insights into user preferences, satisfaction, and emerging trends. These insights enable libraries to offer more personalized and emotionally resonant book recommendations, ensuring that suggested titles align with users' tastes and preferences. Additionally, sentiment analysis supports data-driven decision-making in collection development, allowing libraries to proactively identify popular genres, authors, and topics, as well as detect gaps or underperforming areas in the collection. Ultimately, the application of sentiment analysis in libraries represents a transformative tool for optimizing user experiences, enhancing the relevancy of collections, and fostering stronger connections between libraries and their patrons.*

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis, Book Recommendations, Collection Development, Feedback, Library, Library Services.

Introduction

A library is a vital element of any educational framework and is considered the central component of academic institutions. Its main role is to supply patrons with sufficient and relevant information resources.

A crucial component of library administration mandated by responsibility and self-improvement is the evaluation of the services' efficacy.

User studies are an important aspect of library operations, as they provide insight into user needs, preferences, and perceptions of library services (Wildemuth, 2003).

Libraries “strategic objectives always have been strongly connected with users “perspectives and surveys constitute a communication channel between them (Kettunen, 2007).

The results of user feedback can be used to build more useful services, choose pertinent resources, and provide amenities that will raise user pleasure and improve their perception—especially in the rapidly evolving digital landscape. Additionally, user feedbacks or studies can assist libraries in comprehending how their materials and services affect their patrons. It aids in determining what is effective and what requires improvement. By learning how people are using library resources and making necessary service improvements, user studies can help libraries remain relevant.

Currently, user satisfaction is primarily gauged through questionnaires, which provide a statistical overview of users' perceptions regarding library services.

As a result, users' ratings attempt to depict as eloquently as possible satisfaction states, having the constraint to be expressed within a confined scale (Moore, 2017).

Social media's introduction has significantly altered how people communicate their ideas, opinions, and beliefs throughout the globe. In the last decade, the rapid development of the Internet has generated a huge amount of online comments, and analyzing the sentiments of netizens in comments is of great significance for social stability and development (Birjali et al., 2021).

With the development of ICT and web-based social media platforms give opportunity to track emotion of event that has been visible via text and tweets (Thelwall& Buckley, 2013).

The advent of sentiment analysis has enabled researchers to examine and quantify emotions and opinions conveyed in text, as well as to identify key semantic concepts embedded in user comments.

Sentiment analysis is a natural language processing method assigning a polarity (positive or negative) to textual subjective statements and also identifying and extracting important concepts included within (Nanli, Ping, Weiguo, & Meng, 2012).

Sentiment analysis, a technique that evaluates emotions and opinions in textual data, allows libraries to tap into user feedback, such as reviews, comments, and surveys, to gain deeper insights into user satisfaction.

This paper explores the application of sentiment analysis in libraries, particularly focusing on its potential to enhance book recommendation systems and optimize resource allocation. By analyzing user sentiments expressed in reviews, surveys, and social media, libraries can gain insights into the emotional responses of their users, allowing them to tailor recommendations more effectively, better align their resources, and improve overall service quality, leading to a more personalized and efficient library experience.

Objective

This paper main objective is to discuss how sentiment analysis can be applied in libraries to enhance book recommendation systems and optimize resource allocation by systematically analyzing user feedback, with the goal of improving the relevance of recommendations and making data-driven decisions for better resource management.

Literature Review

While sentiment analysis has been the subject of numerous researches, not many of them deal with libraries. Some research works by Tamaro et al., (2022), similarly, Moore (2017), Kim (2022), Sharma et al., (2021), Deori et al. 2021), Lamba & Madhusudhan, (2018), Parabhoi (2019), Deo et al. (2020), Zou et al. (2020), Patra, (2019), Barnes et al. (2018), Pandey et al. (2017), Thelwall & Buckley (2013), Al-Daihani & Abrahams (2018), Alewine (2012), Hensley & Miller (2010), Gerolimos (2011) and Parabhoi & Saha (2018), Jankowska, Hertel, & Young (2006) etc. have been reviewed for this paper.

“Sentiment Analysis or Opinion Mining is the computational study of people’s opinions, attitudes and emotions toward an entity. The entity can represent individuals, events or topics” (Medhat, Hassan, & Korashy, 2014).

Information science attempted to capitalize that expertise either for the optimization of information retrieval (Hu & Downie, 2010) or for citation analysis (Athar, 2011; Small, 2011). Hu & Downie (2010) implemented sentiment analysis on 5,296 songs in order to achieve automatic music mood classification for songs included in music digital libraries. Mood tags will operate as a practical access point in music collections of digital libraries. Additionally, Small (2011) completed a sentiment citation analysis based on the textual context of the references.

Due to its combination of machine learning, statistical, and linguistic techniques, text mining has become a central field in study since it allows for the automatic examination of large datasets in order to reveal hidden information. Because textual information is unstructured, these methods must be used for a wide range of applications, including information retrieval, topic tracking, topic tracking, summarization, categorization, clustering, and concept linkage, detecting the emotional content of texts in online social networks, data collection, database schemas, and data processing (Hashimi & Hafez, 2015).

The sentiment analysis of user comments on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube videos have been the subject of several studies conducted in the past year (Gopalakrishna Pillai, Thelwall, & Orasan, 2018c; Gopalakrishna Pillai, Thelwall, & Orasan, 2018b).

For example, (Shukri, Yaghi, Aljarah, & Alsawalqah, 2015) attempted to use sentiment analysis and text mining to the automotive sector.

The author of this study analyzed user-posted Twitter data on Audi, BMW, and Mercedes vehicles. Similar to this, (Parabhoi & Saha, 2018) examined comments made on Koha ILS on YouTube. We looked over 404 YouTube comments in all.

Library and information professionals need tools for improvements of communication management in libraries. Academic Libraries operate in a continuously changing landscape and therefore they need to know basic information about their users in order to satisfy their expectations, exploit their feedback and manage users’ expectations (Jankowska, Hertel, & Young, 2006).

As a result, they must examine the origins of comments from various platforms. Gerolimos (2011) conducted an analysis of 3,513 comments on libraries' Facebook page and discovered that most users preferred to express themselves symbolically (e.g., through options) rather than textually. Similar research was conducted and published by Al-Daihani & Abrahams (2018), using a larger dataset

(18,333 unique posts, 113,621 likes, and 3401 comments) from Facebook posts from university libraries. Their primary goal was to analyze how Facebook users of the library interacted with the content that was shared on that particular social media platform.

According to Parabhoi (2019), libraries should take advantage of social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter to conduct sentiment analysis on patrons and learn about their opinions, comments, and feedback regarding the services they have used at university libraries.

Similarly, Deoet al. (2020) applied the VADER sentiment algorithm for predicting the use of books and resources in libraries.

In order to evaluate the level of involvement and attention that Indian public libraries and certain academic institutions receive on social media, Patra (2019) mapped the Twitter activity of these libraries.

In order to improve the service quality and efficiency of the library, Zou et al. (2020) suggested using sentiment analysis as a novel strategy to create a participatory library where patrons may participate in and directly affect the main choices and operations of the library. They looked into the sentiment analysis of the ten public libraries to find out how they use various engagement techniques to keep their patrons interested.

Moore (2017) used sentiment analysis on LibQUAL+ comments for a Canadian academic library to obtain insight into three areas: the place of the library, the impact of the service, and the information control. Implementations of sentiment analysis produced results that were consistent with LibQUAL's + quantitative findings, demonstrating the method's effectiveness.

In order to better serve the evolving needs of their patrons and better understand user perceptions and sentiments, the CSBNO consortium, which oversees 60 libraries in Italy and collaborates with other European libraries, attempted to develop a model for sentiment analysis of library users (Tammaro et al., 2022).

Sharma et al. (2021) made an effort to find out what people thought of the NDLI mobile app and what issues they were having with using it. Using AppBot and AppFollow analytics tools, a sentiment analysis was conducted on the sample of 4560 reviews. The analysis revealed that 2136 of the reviews were positive and 1830 were negative for the NDLI app. The NDLI app receives an overall sentiment score of 66%.

The social view of public libraries in the community was studied by Noh and Kim (2022). Similarly, Lund (2020) used sentiment analysis to find suggestions for management and marketing choices by examining the tweets of prominent publishers as well as leading librarians.

In an experimental investigation, Lamba & Madhusudhan (2018) conducted a case study on aspects of economic productivity to examine the use of sentiment analysis in libraries. Using the RapidMiner platform, a total of 6416 tweets were retrieved by executing 20 distinct productivity-related queries. According to their analysis, the majority of tweets had a neutral polarity, and India ranked second globally in terms of hashtag usage related to productivity, after the United Kingdom.

It is a self-evident truth that libraries which serve distant learners are pressed by the imperative need to come closer to their users' need as the gap between them doesn't facilitate their communication.

Therefore, various studies come to light focusing on this kind of user's satisfaction (Alewine, 2012; Hensley & Miller, 2010).

Methodology:

In order to prepare for this study, we thoroughly reviewed the body of research on the use of sentiment analysis in libraries. Here, we've compiled information from a range of sources, such as academic journals, blogs on the internet, news stories, social media sites, and digital exchanges. This will give the application of sentiment analysis in libraries a theoretical base and help to identify gaps and obstacles in the current state of knowledge. We also address how sentiment analysis might be helpful for improving book recommendations and optimizing resources through user feedback analysis using the extensive literature.

Applications of Sentiment Analysis in Libraries:

Sentiment analysis uses natural language processing (NLP) techniques on normalized sentences that describe views (positive, negative, and neutral) to automatically identify unfavorable opinions about products or services.

Sentiment analysis is applicable anywhere textual data is available and text data needs to be analyzed quickly and effectively to understand how users perceive the resources, facilities, and services provided by libraries. Decisions can then be made with this knowledge in mind, and library services can be improved.

Sentiment analysis is a powerful tool for user research because it makes it possible to analyze vast amounts of data, including social media posts and user reviews of library services. Libraries may find this helpful in promptly recognizing patterns and trends in the views and opinions of its patrons. Furthermore, sentiment analysis can be completed almost instantly compared to content analysis. Libraries can utilize this to monitor shifts in patron perception over time and to react promptly to user feedback.

Some of the areas where sentiment analysis can be applied in libraries are listed below.

Analyzing user feedback on library services: Sentiment analysis is a tool that libraries can use to examine user input on services, including social media posts, online chat transcripts, and survey replies (Joo et al., 2020). Libraries often gather feedback through surveys, comment forms, and social media. Sentiment analysis can process and analyze this data to gauge overall user satisfaction. Libraries can use this information to improve their services, such as refining programs, adjusting hours, or enhancing customer service based on recurring themes in user sentiment. This data-driven approach helps libraries become more proactive in addressing user needs.

Event and Program Evaluation: Libraries frequently host community events, workshops, and educational programs. Sentiment analysis can be applied to feedback from participants, offering insights into the success or areas for improvement of such events. Positive sentiments can indicate popular programs that may warrant expansion, while negative feedback can help libraries refine or reconsider future offerings.

Social Media Monitoring and Public Engagement: Sentiment analysis can be used to track discussions of the library on social media by keeping an eye out for mentions of the institution (Joo et al., 2020). Libraries increasingly engage with their patrons through social media platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram. Sentiment analysis of these interactions can help libraries understand the

public perception of their services and initiatives. It allows for real-time monitoring of user attitudes and helps librarians respond promptly to any issues, capitalize on positive feedback, and increase public engagement through targeted content.

Track the Usage of Library Apps: By conducting online surveys and analyzing the sentiment of the answers, sentiment analysis may be used to investigate user feedback on the digital library and other online services (Deori et al., 2021; Ferilli et al., 2017). The findings can be applied to address problems users encounter when utilizing the library applications and to enhance the user interface.

Improving Catalog and Metadata Search Experience: Sentiment analysis can also be applied to user search behavior and catalog interactions. By analyzing how users feel about the ease of navigating library catalogs or finding materials, libraries can optimize their search interfaces and metadata systems to provide a smoother, more intuitive user experience. Feedback expressing frustration or confusion in finding specific resources can lead to improvements in cataloging and search algorithms.

Academic and Research Services: In academic libraries, sentiment analysis can be used to assess how well research support services, such as reference assistance or digital databases, are meeting the needs of students and faculty. By analyzing feedback from researchers, libraries can identify gaps in service or areas where additional resources may be required, ensuring that academic support remains aligned with the needs of the research community.

Marketing and outreach: Reactions to and interactions with library marketing and outreach initiatives, like comments on Facebook posts and tweets about the library's initiatives, can be examined using sentiment analysis (Lund, 2020). This will assist them in determining which initiatives the users favor and which ones they dislike.

Lastly, the applications of Sentiment analysis on libraries which will be discussed here mainly are ***Book Recommendation Systems&Collection Development.***

Sentiment Analysis-Based Book Recommendation Systems

A significant area of attention for most software developers or effective library management systems is book recommendation. It's critical to support pupils' enthusiasm in reading development so they can understand the material well.

Sentiment analysis-based book recommendation systems leverage the power of natural language processing (NLP) to analyze user-generated content, such as book reviews, ratings, and feedback, to recommend books that align with the emotional and intellectual preferences of readers. Unlike traditional recommendation systems that rely solely on metrics such as genre, author, or user ratings, sentiment analysis adds a deeper layer of understanding by assessing the emotions, attitudes, and opinions expressed in reviews.

By applying sentiment analysis, libraries and digital platforms can extract insights from user feedback to identify whether a book elicited positive, negative, or neutral emotions. For example, if a user tends to enjoy books with positive or uplifting themes, the system can prioritize recommending books that have been described in similar terms by other readers. Conversely, if a user expresses a preference for books that evoke deeper, more intense emotions, the system can recommend titles that have garnered reviews reflecting those sentiments.

This method of recommendation can significantly enhance the personalization of book suggestions. Instead of relying only on quantitative data like star ratings, sentiment analysis allows for a qualitative approach, which considers the nuanced emotional responses readers have to different books. For example, a book might have a high rating, but reviews might suggest that it appeals to a specific type of reader or mood. By analyzing this sentiment, libraries can offer more targeted recommendations that resonate better with individual users.

Sentiment analysis-based recommendation systems also help in discovering hidden gems—books that may not be widely popular but have received deeply positive feedback from a smaller group of readers. This ensures that users receive more diverse recommendations that go beyond mainstream or best-seller lists.

Furthermore, such systems can continually improve as they gather more feedback. Over time, they learn more about individual user preferences and evolving trends, allowing for adaptive and increasingly accurate book recommendations. This enhances the overall user experience, leading to greater engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty among library patrons or users of digital platforms.

By integrating sentiment analysis into recommendation systems, libraries can create a more dynamic, emotionally resonant experience for readers, encouraging exploration and fostering a deeper connection between users and their reading material.

In any academic setting, it is seen that students who choose to refer extensively to books for a given subject have a higher chance of earning good grades and also strengthen their analytical and writing skills.

One method for making recommendations based on the responses of users who are similar to you is called **collaborative filtering**. It involves groups with comparable preferences, enabling more insightful recommendations. A library has a vast collection of materials on many different subjects. This makes data management challenging. This necessitates effective information filtering methods. When a user indicates which library materials he prefers, the system compares his ratings to those of other users to identify those who have made the most comparable selections. Therefore, collaborative filtering can help address this problem and enable users to quickly and simply explore the resources based on their interests.

A specific application can be used to determine how each member rates the books individually in order to give it another go for students or individuals with comparable ratings. Students with comparable interests will receive better search results as a result.

Using Sentiment Analysis for Collection Development in Libraries

Understanding User Preferences through Sentiment Analysis:

Sentiment analysis, a branch of natural language processing (NLP), is used to evaluate user feedback and identify the emotional tone behind it. By applying sentiment analysis to user reviews, comments, and social media discussions about books or other library resources, libraries can gauge user satisfaction and preferences more precisely.

Analyzing Feedback for Collection Relevance: Sentiment analysis enables libraries to process large volumes of user feedback and detect whether users have positive, negative, or neutral sentiments about

specific resources. For instance, if a particular book or genre receives consistently positive feedback, it may signal an area where the library should expand its collection. Conversely, negative feedback on outdated or unpopular materials can help identify items for weeding or replacement.

Refining Genre and Subject Focus: Libraries can use sentiment analysis to refine their focus on particular genres or subjects that resonate with users. For example, if sentiment analysis reveals growing positive emotions toward science fiction, graphic novels, or environmental literature, the library can allocate more budget to acquire additional resources in these areas. This ensures the collection stays aligned with current user interests.

Personalizing Collection to Diverse Needs: Different user groups may have distinct preferences, and sentiment analysis can help libraries understand these variations. For instance, young adult users might express strong positive sentiments about fantasy or contemporary young adult fiction, while academic researchers might show more interest in specific fields like technology or social sciences. By analyzing feedback from various demographic groups, libraries can tailor their collections to suit the diverse needs of their community.

Identifying Trends and Gaps in the Collection:

Sentiment analysis can help libraries identify emerging trends in user preferences and detect gaps in the collection that may not be immediately visible through circulation statistics.

Tracking Emerging Topics: By analyzing online discussions, book reviews, and social media conversations, libraries can use sentiment analysis to spot emerging topics or trends that might not yet be reflected in their collections. For example, a rise in positive sentiment toward books on mental health, climate change, or digital innovation can signal that the library should acquire more materials in these areas to meet user demand.

Filling Gaps in Underrepresented Areas: Sentiment analysis can also highlight areas where users feel the collection is lacking. Negative sentiments or comments expressing frustration about the unavailability of certain types of books, topics, or authors can help libraries identify gaps in the collection. This feedback allows libraries to address those gaps by acquiring new materials or enhancing existing offerings.

Improving Decision-Making for Acquisitions and Weeding:

Sentiment analysis can guide libraries in making more data-driven decisions regarding the acquisition of new materials and the removal of outdated or low-interest items (weeding).

Data-Driven Acquisitions: Traditionally, acquisitions decisions were based on circulation data, librarian expertise, or user requests. With sentiment analysis, libraries can use a more holistic approach by considering the emotional reactions of users toward certain genres, authors, or subjects. For example, books that generate strong positive sentiment across user reviews can be prioritized for acquisition. This ensures that libraries invest in materials that are likely to engage users and be of high interest.

Efficient Weeding: Sentiment analysis can also assist in identifying resources that are no longer relevant or appreciated by the library's user base. If certain books or collections consistently receive negative feedback or are rarely discussed in a positive light, this may indicate that they are outdated,

irrelevant, or underperforming. Libraries can use this data to make informed decisions about which materials to remove, ensuring that the collection remains fresh and appealing.

Enhancing User-Centered Collection Development:

Sentiment analysis promotes a user-centered approach to collection development by aligning the library's offerings with the emotional and intellectual needs of its patrons. By listening to user feedback and analyzing the sentiments behind it, libraries can develop a more personalized and engaging collection.

Personalized Content Curation: Libraries can use sentiment analysis to personalize the collection based on the emotional responses of their users. For example, if sentiment analysis reveals that certain books evoke strong positive emotions in specific user segments (e.g., mystery lovers or history enthusiasts), libraries can acquire more content in those areas. This personalized approach helps build a collection that feels more relevant and responsive to users' tastes.

Enhancing User Satisfaction and Engagement: By focusing on materials that generate positive sentiment, libraries can increase user satisfaction and engagement. When users feel that their preferences and feedback are valued, they are more likely to engage with the library's resources, both physically and digitally. Sentiment analysis helps libraries stay in tune with their community's needs and ensure their collection reflects the interests of their patrons.

Challenges of Applying Sentiment Analysis in Libraries

Although sentiment analysis provides insightful information, there are a number of issues to take into account:

Availability of Feedback Data: Data on user feedback availability is one of the main obstacles. It can be challenging to gather enough information without focused efforts in order to carry out an exhaustive study. This is especially true for libraries, as they frequently have poor social media involvement and receive insignificant enough comments on postings about libraries to warrant further investigation.

Data Privacy: When assessing comments or reviews, libraries must make sure that user data is protected and anonymized to protect the privacy of its patrons.

Complexity of Interpretation: Since sentiment analysis depends on accurate language interpretation, varied user populations with a wide range of linguistic and cultural expressions may provide difficulties. If not adequately taken into consideration, sarcasm, humor, or confusing wording might bias results.

Integration with Current Systems: Librarians may encounter challenges when attempting to integrate sentiment analysis software with existing catalog or management systems. Training employees and making investments in new technology may be necessary to ensure smooth data collecting and processing.

Language Limitations: Moreover, sentiment analysis algorithms are frequently limited to English, which makes it challenging to analyze text in other languages. Moreover, the work gets significantly more difficult when handling content in many languages.

Conclusion

Sentiment analysis has a promising future in book recommendation and collection building, giving libraries a strong tool to improve personalization, maximize resource utilization, and build collections that genuinely capture the interests and feelings of their patrons. Sentiment analysis will be crucial in forming the next wave of library services, which will be more interactive, user-focused, and data-driven as libraries embrace digital transformation and sophisticated analytics. Libraries will be able to provide individualized experiences that satisfy the intellectual and emotional demands of varied groups by carefully fusing sentiment analysis with AI and machine learning. As a result, libraries will become indispensable centers of knowledge and culture in the digital age.

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